

Recommended citation: Krechetov, I., & Romanenko, V. (2020). Adaptive Learning Technologies in Tsur University. In van der Veen, J., van Hattum-Janssen, N., Järvinen, H.-M., de Laet, T., & ten Dam, I. (Eds.), *Engaging Engineering Education. SEFI 48th Annual Conference* (pp. 269-276). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Enschede, The Netherlands. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14653771.

ADAPTIVE LEARNING TECHNOLOGIES IN TUSUR UNIVERSITY

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Conference Key Areas: *E-learning, Blended learning*

Keywords: *Adaptive learning, Genetic algorithm, Ebbinghaus forgetting curve*

ABSTRACT

One of the popular educational technologies today is adaptive learning. TUSUR has been conducting research in the field of adaptive learning since 2013. Models, algorithms, techniques, and software have been developed to create adaptive e-learning courses for a wide range of disciplines. These technologies are based on the elements of artificial intelligence and predictive analysis of the knowledge level (forgetting curve).

The presentation will show the experience of TUSUR University in the task of development and testing in the real educational process of an adaptive e-learning course. The basic approaches in content design will disclose as well.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Project purpose and objectives

The need for continuous learning and the acquisition of new skills does not fit well with the concept of consistent, structured, static learning offered by familiar LMS systems. A training course in which the instructor designs the content and then presents it in a certain logical sequence is well suited for classical full-time education. But a modern online course must be so dynamic that it generates personal learning trajectories "on the fly". An adaptive learning course should be based on a model of the learner to offer him or her at any moment the optimal (in terms of knowledge level, presentation form, etc.) element of content.

Thus, the objective of the project is to develop an adaptive learning platform and to pilot it on the case of developing and implementing an adaptive learning course. For this purpose, the following tasks need to be solved:

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1. To design and implement an adaptive learning platform. This task has already been solved and the results have been published, so the development of the platform is not described in this article. Only general information about it is given.
2. To develop rules of preparation of learning materials as well as necessary tools for creating an adaptive course.
3. To implement and integrate an adaptive course into the learning process.
4. Evaluate the impact of using adaptive technology in training.

1.2 Project history

The Laboratory of Instrumental Modelling and Learning Systems (LISMO) of the TUSUR Institute of Innovation has been developing the concept of an adaptive learning platform since 2013 [1, 2]. The concept has been based on:

- Breaking down the learning material of the discipline into modules;
- dividing the competences learned in the course of the discipline into subcompetences (learning outcomes);
- measurement of students' knowledge level in each subcompetence on the basis of testing;
- extrapolation of students' knowledge level using Ebbinghaus forgetting curve [3];
- fixation of the studied material in long-term memory on the basis of repetition effect [4].

In 2017 the first software implementation of the platform was released [5, 6]. In 2018 for the National University of Science and Technology MISIS was created an adaptive course in the discipline "Chemistry" [7, 8]. This article describes its development and experience of its use in the learning process.

1.3 Difference from existing solutions

There are several companies on the market that offer ready-made solutions for adaptive learning. These include companies such as Knewton², Khan Academy³, as well as Pearson Education⁴, McGraw-Hill Education⁵, and others. However, a number of factors hinder the use of the adaptive courses they offer in the Russian Federation in general, and in TUSUR in particular:

1. Language barrier. The overwhelming majority of disciplines in the Russian Federation are taught in Russian. Meanwhile, finding Russian-language adaptive courses from publishers in Europe or the USA is very problematic or impossible at all.
2. Availability of tools. Adaptive learning platforms from these companies and publishers are closed. That is, they certainly have their tools for filling adaptive courses with content, but they do not provide them for public access. Therefore, the development of new adaptive courses is only possible within these companies and publishers.

² <https://www.knewton.com/>

³ <https://www.khanacademy.org/>

⁴ <https://www.pearson.com/>

⁵ <https://www.mheducation.com/>

3. A question of scale. From the previous paragraph follows the high cost of custom development of a new adaptive course, which is justified only if the launch of such courses has a high commercial potential and the number of participants in one course starts from 10,000 students or more.

Therefore, the development of an adaptive learning platform with open tools and the possibility of implementation into the existing LMS used in higher education institutions is relevant, making the development of their own adaptive courses appropriate even for small educational institutions.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Content preparation

At the initial stage of developing an adaptive course, a team of methodologists should break down all the material of the discipline into modules and competencies. This is a rather time-consuming process.

Fig. 1. General presentation of the module

Modules (Fig. 1) are indivisible, autonomous units, carrying enough information (text, graphic, multimedia) to unambiguously define the output skills and knowledge (competencies) that the trainee will acquire after mastering this module [1]. The competence tree is presented as a link diagram (or memory card). Further, for each module, a document (in the format of Microsoft Word, OpenOffice Writer, HTML, etc.) is prepared, including the module name, its content, as well as a list of questions for the test, allowing to check the level of knowledge of students on the output competences after studying the module. And, finally, a table (Microsoft Excel, OpenOffice Calc, etc.) is compiled for describing the links between modules and competencies. Thus, the set of modules and competences of an adaptive course forms a directional bipartite graph [2].

2.2 Algorithm for providing modules to students

If the stage of modules and competences design is completed responsibly, the adaptive course is able to work completely autonomously in the training process, independently deciding the further trajectory of training, providing students with training modules, testing their knowledge, and collecting analytics.

The general block diagram of the algorithm is shown in Fig. 2. Here P is the graph-path (the path in the graph, passing through the unexplored modules in such a way as to provide the maximum average level of remaining knowledge of a student at the moment of the end of course), S is the student model, consisting of the history of his learning, and individually selected coefficients of Ebbinghaus forgetting curves as well [3].

Fig. 2. General block diagram of the adaptive learning algorithm

The algorithm uses two basic concepts. The first is the choice of the optimal learning path P as the solution of the genetic algorithm of the optimization task

$$F(P) = \frac{\sum_i TM_i}{\sum_j R_j} \rightarrow \min, \quad (1)$$

Here TM_i is the time required to study the P_i module from the proposed path, R_j is the predicted level of knowledge of a student in K_j competence at the time of graduation. Thus, the genetic algorithm minimizes the time spent on studying the residual material, while trying to ensure the maximum level of remaining knowledge. The second concept is the use of Ebbinghaus forgetting curves to predict the remaining level of knowledge of the student in each competence of the course. Initially, each student in his model S is assigned coefficients of the Ebbinghaus forgetting curve with default values. But during further training, they are corrected, providing unique behavior of the algorithm for each student.

2.3 Toolkit for creating an adaptive course

At present the toolkit is made as a plugin for LMS Moodle (Fig. 3). This toolkit allows the author of an adaptive course [5, 6]:

- to fill the course with modules and competences;
- to link the modules with each other, specifying their input and output competences;
- link the competences with tests that measure the level of knowledge of these competences;
- follow the progress of students, receiving various kinds of analytics.

Fig. 3. Adaptive Course Developer Interface

Since adaptive courses are used not only in distance learning but also in face-to-face teaching, it is possible to add competences to the base, for which grades can only be obtained from the teacher. For example, it can be laboratory work – first, the student studies the necessary theory in an electronic adaptive course, performs tests, etc., and then the laboratory work is performed directly at the university and passed before the teacher. Correspondingly, there is a tool for setting the level of knowledge on such competences. But, as mentioned above, their inclusion in the adaptive course is not mandatory, i.e. it can function fully independently.

2.4 Procedure for developing adaptive courses

Thus, according to the proposed methodology, the development of an adaptive course is carried out in the following order:

1. The authors of the course (teachers or methodologists) prepare all necessary materials (description of competencies, modules, tests). For this purpose, a special instruction was developed, which specifies the principles of decomposition of training material into modules and competencies, as well as the format of their description.
2. Technical specialists parse the prepared materials and import metadata into the system. Metadata sets the course structure (linking modules, competencies, and tests) and properties of its elements. After that, the layout designer handles the content of the course modules, and the testing specialist handles the layout of the test questions.
3. Technical specialists perform the final assembly and adjustment of the adaptive course, as well as its test run. Its purpose is to make sure that the trajectories offered by the system coincide with the expected trajectories. After that, the test run is performed by the authors of the course. If any deficiencies are detected, technical experts will edit the metadata and course content.

4. A ready-made adaptive course is provided to the trainees. The analytics collected in the course of its operation allows, among other things, to identify defects in course design (for example, too simple or too complex elements of the course). Therefore, all the necessary tools are now available, as well as a well-tried procedure for creating adaptive training courses. The described methodology has been tested in the process of creating the adaptive course "General Chemistry" for MISIS.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Results of the adaptive course approbation

When teaching the discipline "General Chemistry", the model of blended learning based on "inverted class" technology was used [7, 8]. The traditional structure of "General Chemistry" course includes three types of activities: lectures, practical and laboratory classes. Each type of classroom sessions was supplemented by an adaptive component implemented in an LMS environment.

The effectiveness of the adaptive course can be assessed on the basis of the diagram is shown in Fig. 4. On the ordinate axis, the percentage of students who have successfully coped with the examining activity by certain activity type is given. Test groups were selected from a single stream of the same specialization, taught by one teacher.

Fig. 4. Approbation results

The chart shows that the performance of students from the experimental group (using adaptive learning) in all types of control activities is significantly higher than students learning the program in the traditional format.

Thus, all the tasks of the project have been completed. The implementation of the created course proved the effectiveness of adaptive learning technology in general and the effectiveness of the developed platform in particular. Therefore, a new

adaptive course in the discipline "Mathematics" for MISIS is already being developed and a number of other courses for different universities are planned to be developed.

3.2 Further development of the platform

The platform is currently being actively developed. Accordingly, the additional functionality described below can be used when developing new adaptive courses. Firstly, there are new possibilities to set up links between modules. The practice has shown that in some cases, the learning path can loop when a student can not pass the exit test after studying the next module, and there are no alternative modules to study at the moment. Therefore, it is possible to establish additional links that describe possible paths for further study. For example, with references to previously studied material: it is possible that it is precisely what a student has poorly learned prevents him or her from progressing further in the course.

For this purpose, new concepts - "prerequisite" and "marker" - have been introduced. Prerequisites to module M are other modules that a student should have studied sometime before (perhaps even within another previous discipline). Initially, they are not placed into the path but appear in it if the student was unable to pass module M. Markers are a more subtle tool. Markers mark individual questions in tests, and it depends on the correctness of the answer to the question whether the module to which the marker points will be included in the further path or not.

Gradation of modules by types has also been added. For example, a diagnostic module allows a student to exclude from the trajectory whole sections of a discipline if the student is already familiar with them.

Secondly, the concept of platform implementation in the form of a cloud solution independent of the specific LMS is being developed. Integration into LMS will be done with the help of LTI or xAPI standards. This will also allow to take into account the student's progress in other disciplines, if it is preserved, for example, in the LRS (Learning Record Store). On the other hand, a student's progress in an adaptive course can be preserved in the LRS, many of which have powerful learning information analytics tools.

Thirdly, the adaptive course developer toolkit is being developed in the way it is not dependent on the LMS Moodle. For example, a trial version of the module and competence editor has been implemented on the Semantic MediaWiki⁶ platform. In general, the author's team has the concept of creating a common interdisciplinary storage of modules and competences. Then it will be easy to include into one discipline topics from other disciplines, as well as take into account the progress of mastering competencies from one discipline to another. In addition, it would allow using modules from other disciplines as preconditions. In this way, an integrated adaptive learning process will be created from the moment students enter the university until the moment they graduate.

⁶ <https://www.semantic-mediawiki.org/>

REFERENCES

- [1] Krechetov I.A. Algoritm generacii posledovatel'nosti obrazovatel'nyh modulej v tekhnologii polucheniya adaptivnogo obrazovatel'nogo kontenta // Materialy dokladov vtorogo Mezhdunarodnogo Pospelovskogo simpoziuma «Gibridnye i sinergeticheskie intellektual'nye sistemy» (GISIS 2014, g. Svetlogorsk). – S. 200–206.
- [2] Krechetov I.A. Ob odnom algoritme adaptivnogo obucheniya na osnove krivoj zabyvaniya / I.A. Krechetov, V.V. Kruchinin // Doklady TUSUR. – 2017. – №1. – pp. 75–80.
- [3] Lange, V.N. (1983), O skorosti zabyvaniya, Voprosy psihologii, №4, pp. 142-145.
- [4] Bujmov A.G. Veroyatnostnaya model' effekta povtorenij v obuchenii / A.G. Bujmov, B.A. Bujmov // Doklady TUSUR. – 2010. – №1, ch. 2. – pp. 236–242.
- [5] Krechetov I.A., Romanenko V.V. Realizaciya i vnedrenie tekhnologii adaptivnogo obucheniya v universitete / Materialy mezhdunarodnoj nauchno-metodicheskoy konferencii "Sovremennoe obrazovanie: povyschenie professional'noj kompetentnosti prepodavatelej vuza - garantiya obespecheniya kachestva obrazovaniya". 2018. pp. 191-192.
- [6] Krechetov I.A., Romanenko V.V., Kruchinin V.V., Gorodovich A.V. Realizaciya adaptivnogo obucheniya: metody i tekhnologii / Otkrytoe i distancionnoe obrazovanie. 2018. №3 (71). pp. 33-39.
- [7] Krechetov I.A., Dorofeeva M.YU., Degtyarev A.V. Raskryvaem potencial adaptivno-go obucheniya: ot razrabotki do vnedreniya // Materialy Mezhdunarodnoj konferencii «eLearning Stakeholders and Researchers Summit 2018». – M: Izd. dom Vysshej shkoly eko-nomiki, 2018. – pp. 76-85.
- [8] Krechetov I.A., Romanenkov V.V., Dorofeeva M.YU., Degtyarev A.V. Rezul'taty vnedreniya adaptivnogo elektronno-go kursa v uchebnyj process / Materialy mezhdunarodnoj nauchno-metodicheskoy konferencii "Sovremennoe obrazovanie: kachestvo obrazovaniya i aktual'nye problemy sovremennoj vysshej shkoly". 2019. pp. 116-118.